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The 3D pressure-dependent elasto-plastic constitutive model within tension-compression asymmetry and its application to predict laminates' responses under off-axis loading conditions

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Main Contents

- 1 Background
- 2 Objective
- 3 Constitutive modeling
- 4 Determination of model parameters
- 5 Numerical implementation procedures
- 6 Validation by experiments
- 7 Conclusions

Background

Objective

A newly formulated elastoplastic constitutive model for UD laminates.

Constitutive Modeling

- The plastic potential function

$$g = \frac{1}{2} \left[(\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})^2 + 2\Gamma a_{66} (\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2) + 2a_{44} \sigma_{23}^2 \right] + \frac{1}{3} a_{11} (\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})^2 + \frac{1}{3} (\Gamma - 1) (\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})^2 \text{sig}(\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})$$

- The yield criterion and the effective stress

$$F(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff}}^p) = \sigma_{\text{eff}} - R(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff}}^p)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{eff}} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} \left[(\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})^2 + 2\Gamma a_{66} (\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2) + 2a_{44} \sigma_{23}^2 \right] + a_{11} (\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})^2 + (\Gamma - 1) (\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})^2 \text{sig}(\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})}$$

- Non-associative flow rule

$$d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p = d\lambda^p \cdot \frac{\partial g}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}$$

- The Kuhn-tucker loading condition (Simo et.al, 2000)

$$F \leq 0; \quad \dot{\lambda}^p \geq 0; \quad F \dot{\lambda}^p = 0; \quad \dot{F} = 0.$$

Constitutive Modeling

- The incremental plastic strain

$$d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p = \begin{bmatrix} d\varepsilon_{11}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{22}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{33}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{12}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{23}^p \\ d\varepsilon_{13}^p \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2}{3} d\lambda^p \cdot \begin{bmatrix} a_{11}(\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) \\ \frac{3}{2}(\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33}) + a_{11}(\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) + (\Gamma - 1)(\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})\text{sig}(\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) \\ -\frac{3}{2}(\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33}) + a_{11}(\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) + (\Gamma - 1)(\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})\text{sig}(\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) \\ 3\Gamma a_{66}\sigma_{12} \\ 3\Gamma a_{44}\sigma_{23} \\ 3\Gamma a_{66}\sigma_{13} \end{bmatrix}$$

- The isotropic strain hardening law

$$R(\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^p) = \begin{cases} R_{0T} + A_{1T} \cdot e^{-\frac{\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^p}{B_{1T}}} + A_{2T} \cdot e^{-\frac{\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^p}{B_{2T}}} + A_{3T} \cdot e^{-\frac{\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^p}{B_{3T}}}; & \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33} > 0 \\ R_{0C} + A_{1C} \cdot e^{-\frac{\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^p}{B_{1C}}} + A_{2C} \cdot e^{-\frac{\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^p}{B_{2C}}} + A_{3C} \cdot e^{-\frac{\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^p}{B_{3C}}}; & \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33} \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

Determination of model parameters

$$\sigma_{11} = \sigma_x \cos^2 \theta$$

$$\sigma_{22} = \sigma_x \sin^2 \theta$$

$$\sigma_{12} = -\sigma_x \sin \theta \cos \theta$$

$$d\varepsilon_x^p = d\varepsilon_{11}^p \cos^2 \theta + d\varepsilon_{22}^p \sin^2 \theta - 2d\varepsilon_{12}^p \sin \theta \cos \theta$$

$$\sigma_{\text{eff}} = h(\theta) \cdot |\sigma_x|$$

$$\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}^p = \frac{|\sigma_x|}{h(\theta) \cdot \sigma_x} \cdot \left(\varepsilon_x - \frac{\sigma_x}{E_x} \right)$$

$$h(\theta) = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} \sin^4 \theta + 3\Gamma a_{66} \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta + a_{11} + (\Gamma - 1) \sin^4 \theta \cdot \text{sig}(\sigma_x)}$$

(Zhu et.al, 2013)

Numerical implementation procedures

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n + \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1},$$

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^p = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n^p + \Delta \lambda_{n+1}^p \cdot \partial_{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \boldsymbol{g}_{n+1},$$

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n+1}^p = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n}^p + \frac{2}{3} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{eff},n+1} \cdot \Delta \lambda_{n+1}^p,$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_n + \boldsymbol{C} : (\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1} - \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^p),$$

$$F(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1}(\Delta \lambda_{n+1}^p), \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{eff},n+1}^p(\Delta \lambda_{n+1}^p)) \leq 0.$$

Validation by Experiments

Case A	HTS40/PA6 carbon/polyamide composite, Vf=46%, (Wang et.al 2019)	Monotonic tension and compression test, Cyclic loading and unloading tests.
Case B	IM600/Q133 carbon/epoxy composite, (Zhu et.al 2013)	Off-axis tension and compression test.
Case C	T800H/3633 carbon/epoxy composite, Vf=57%, (Yokozeki et.al, 2007)	Off-axis tension and compression test.

Validation by Experiments

Case A HTS40/PA6

(a)

(b)

Specimen geometry (dimensions in mm) :
(a) tension (b) compression

Experimental configuration
(Wang et.al, 2019)

FEA models
(C3D8, mesh size of 1mm)

Case B IM600/Q133

(a) Tension (b) Compression
Experimental configuration
 (Zhu et.al, 2013)

FEA models
 (C3D8, mesh size of 1mm)

Case C

Specimen configuration :
 (left) compression test, (right) tension test ;
Experimental configuration
 (Yokozeki et.al, 2007)

FEA models
 (C3D8, mesh size of 1mm)

HTS40/PA6

IM600/Q133

T800H/3633

Effective stress-effective plastic strain curves (a) tension tests (b) compression tests.

HTS40/PA6

IM600/Q133

T800H/3633

Stress-strain curves in (a) tension tests and (b) compression tests.

Conclusions

- Advantages

- a. Predicting the **tension and compression asymmetry** of UD laminates subjected to loading conditions.
- b. Allows for the consideration of **hydrostatic pressure dependence** and **nonlinearity along the fiber direction**.
- c. The more simplified formulation of incremental plastic strain was obtained within the non-associative flow rule.

- Further research

- a. Further validation on the capability of predicting nonlinearity along fiber direction in natural fiber composite.
- b. Appropriate ways of obtaining model parameters by decoupling the damage and plasticity coupling effects in off-axis loading test results.
- c. Extensions by including strain rate effect of FRP mechanical behaviors.

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